

Multi-actor co-innovation partnerships in agriculture, forestry and related sectors in Europe: Contrasting approaches to implementation

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Multi-actor partnerships adopt contrasting approaches to co-innovation according to contextual contingencies.
- Based on evidence from 200 diverse partnerships, we developed a typology of eight ‘ideal types’ of co-innovation activity.
- One dimension of the typology is ‘the structural components of the Organisational Innovation System’, with four categories.
- The other is ‘attitude of actors towards interaction’ with two categories.
- Our findings will help policy makers and programme managers to shape targeted interventions for ‘speeding up’ innovation.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Effectiveness of co-innovation by a multi-actor partnership

		Attitude towards interaction	
		Fosters interaction	Indifferent towards interaction
Structural components of the Organisational Innovation System	The actors	Diverse engagement	Focused effort
	The innovation process	Inclusive community	Structured organisation
	Dissemination and embedding	Open network	Targeted activity
	The enabling environment	Action mobilises support	Self-sufficient venture

Conceptual typology of eight ‘ideal types’

Introduction

- Policy context and the need to optimise co-innovation
- Contrasting approaches to co-innovation – no ‘one size fits all’ approach

Methodology

- Analysis of 200 co-innovation partnerships (projects and other ‘actor configurations’) from across Europe

Conclusions

- Each ideal type represents an organisational form that *might* exist, not real partnerships
- No one approach is ‘superior’ but may be more ‘appropriate’ in given circumstances

Policy implications

- Actor needs and local circumstances determine the optimal approach to co-innovation
- ‘The more participation, the better’ does not always apply

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ABSTRACT

CONTEXT: Innovation is an important driver of increased productivity, sustainability and resilience in agriculture, forestry and related sectors. An analysis of how different types of multi-actor co-innovation partnerships function can help to identify the reasons why some are more successful than others in ‘speeding up’ innovation. **OBJECTIVE:** To provide a framework for the analysis of the co-innovation process, we developed a multidimensional conceptual typology of co-innovation activities based on a review of 200 such partnerships involving farmers and foresters from across Europe. This framework is based on innovation systems theory and the prevailing policy context of the ‘multi-actor approach’.

METHODS: The overarching concept or dependent variable measured by the typology is ‘effectiveness of co-innovation by a multi-actor partnership’ and the two dimensions of the overarching concept are the ‘structural components of the Organisational Innovation System’, with four categories, and ‘attitude towards interaction’, with two categories. The result is a matrix of eight ‘ideal types’ of co-innovation activity. These eight types are characterised according to first-order constructs derived from our research data.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS: The results show that the co-innovation process can successfully take contrasting forms according to the ‘contextual contingencies’ encountered by the partnership. In other words, no one ideal

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type is intrinsically 'superior' to another but may be more 'appropriate' in given circumstances. Factors influencing approaches to implementation include actor capacities, aspirations and networks, the co-innovation topic and its influence on the partnership size and the workplan structure, the type of co-innovation activity outputs and the need to engage with the 'larger periphery' of stakeholders, and the nature of the enabling environment. **SIGNIFICANCE:** The typology is not a classification since the ideal types represent organisational forms that might exist rather than real partnerships. However, the analytical framework it provides will help policy makers and programme managers to develop targeted interventions, according to actor needs and local circumstances, for 'speeding up' innovation.

1. Introduction

Demand for food and agricultural products is increasing because the world's population is growing (to a projected 9.6 billion people in 2050) and incomes are rising in much of the developing world. To satisfy this additional demand, a 60% increase in global food production beyond 2005–2007 levels will be necessary by 2050 (Alexandratos and Bruin-sma, 2012). This extra production will place additional stress on land, water and biodiversity, which are already at risk of degradation. Climate disruption is posing its own challenges to food production, while agriculture itself is a major source of greenhouse gas emissions. Meanwhile, despite remarkable advances in poverty reduction in many countries, substantial levels of poverty remain in large parts of the developing world, especially in rural areas (FAO, 2014).

In its influential publication *Save and Grow*, FAO proposed a new paradigm of intensive farm production to address these challenges, one that is both highly productive and environmentally sustainable (FAO, 2011). More recently, the policy focus has expanded to three interrelated goals and outcomes: improving productivity and environmental sustainability simultaneously; and increasing resilience, that is, the capacity of the system to absorb the impacts of adverse events, recover from them, and adapt and transform in response to uncertainty and a changing risk environment in the future (OECD, 2020). In parallel, the United Nations' Zero Hunger Initiative called for reducing food waste (to zero) and over-consumption (Schmidt and Matthies, 2018) while guaranteeing year-round access to adequate food by redressing inequitable food distribution (D'Odorico et al., 2019).

'Innovation', which may be defined as "the process by which individuals or organizations master and implement the design and production of goods and services that are new to them" (Mytelka, 2000), is widely recognised as an important driver of change in this regard (e.g. OECD, 2020). According to this definition, the nature of (agricultural) innovation can be both technological (e.g. agricultural inputs, machinery or crop management techniques) as well as institutional (markets, policies and new forms of social organisation), or a combination of these (Schut et al., 2018). Klerkx et al. (2012) emphasised the co-evolutionary nature of the process, i.e. combined technological, social, economic and institutional change.

The 'multi-actor' project LIAISON (Better Rural Innovation: Linking Actors, Instruments and Policies through Networks), funded by the European Union's (EU) Horizon 2020 (H2020) research and innovation programme, sought to identify why some innovation partnerships are more successful than others in 'speeding up' innovation. The research included a review of 200 multi-actor partnerships involving farmers and foresters from across Europe (Fieldsend et al., 2021). Of the 200 partnerships, 162 were 'projects' (i.e. single, non-divisible interventions with fixed time schedules and dedicated budgets, as defined by O'Neill et al., 2012) and 38 were other 'actor configurations' (sensu Knierim et al., 2015) such as clusters and networks. It was concluded that innovation could successfully be delivered by a wide range of multi-actor partnerships including projects funded by various EU and non-EU programmes, as well as by self-funded innovation activities (Fieldsend et al., 2021). Having shown that there is no single 'ideal' way to innovate, the need for a framework ('typology') that can be used to analyse these contrasting approaches to implementation became

apparent.

2. Organisational innovation systems and multi-actor co-innovation

Innovation does not occur in a vacuum but rather is an evolutionary, non-linear and iterative learning process that is situated in a complex, multi-dimensional system that determines its speed, outputs and, to varying degrees, its direction. Hence, in the literature, much attention has been given to the concept of innovation systems. The topic has been addressed at two levels (Cronin et al., 2022), the first of which is the *macro* level of the Agricultural (Knowledge and) Innovation System (A (K)IS) (e.g. Coenen and Díaz López, 2010). By contrast, the Organisational Innovation System (OIS) approach of Van Lancker et al. (2016), which they defined (p.42) as "innovation network[s] of diverse actors, collaborating with a focal innovating organization in an innovation process, to generate, develop and commercialize a new concept, shaped by institutions", focusses on the *micro* level.

Van Lancker et al. (2016) described four structural components of the OIS: (a) the actors, (b) the innovation process, (c) the innovation network and (d) the institutions. The *actors* are those groups or individuals who have a stake in the innovation process. The authors argued that the *innovation process* within the OIS has three main phases, the *innovative idea*, which is developed into an *invention*, which in turn is followed by *commercialisation*. Bogers (2011) suggested that the *innovation network* consists of two layers. The first is a smaller, 'core group' of actors with whom the organisation works in close collaboration, sharing knowledge openly. The second layer consists of a 'larger periphery' of diverse stakeholders that are less involved, though they participate in the innovation process, with whom not all information is shared. These stakeholders help create legitimacy and support for the innovation (Turner et al., 2016). Finally, the *institutions* that regulate the process are the legal (e.g. regulation and law) and 'customarily institutions' (e.g. culture and values) that together constitute the 'rules of the game' or the 'codes of conduct' (Klein Woolthuis et al., 2005). There is a clear distinction between institutions and organisations: the former correspond to rules and the latter are players (ibid.).

As indicated above, innovation frequently takes place in the frame of projects and during the last 20 years the 'project' has become a key form of contemporary governance and policy implementation (Büttner and Leopold, 2016). Sjoblom and Godenhjelm (2009) described the project as "a post-modern symbol of adaptability and contingency – it is thought of as a superior way of reacting to unforeseen and non-standard situations". Projects can be conceptualised as temporary organisations (Sydow and Braun, 2018) and Fieldsend et al. (2020) showed that the OIS concept, with the 'multi-actor partnership' placed at the core of an OIS, can be applied to projects and other forms of innovation actions in agriculture, forestry and related sectors. The core group of *actors* constitute the partnership which engages with a larger periphery of engaged stakeholders (the *innovation network*) in the *innovation process*.

Citing Lundvall (1992), Coenen and Díaz López (2010) noted that innovations are iteratively enacted through networks of social relations rather than through singular events by isolated individuals or organisations. This recognition among academics and policy makers that knowledge *sharing* occurs between actors, and that this is 'two-way',

from ‘experts’ to ‘practitioners’ and vice versa (Lowe et al., 2019) has led to increasing interest in the concept of ‘interactive’ rather than ‘linear’ innovation. The conceptual validity of interactive (or co-)innovation has been elaborated by many authors (e.g. Johannessen, 2009; Klerkx et al., 2012; Schut et al., 2018). However, a note of caution is necessary. Co-innovation is occurring alongside, and not replacing, the traditional process of ‘knowledge transfer’. We do not support the statement of Ujj et al. (2020), attributed to Dolinska and d’Aquino (2016), concerning “the failure of the linear model in knowledge transfer” since knowledge never “only flowed in one direction” (i.e. from researcher to practitioner). Indeed, participation in agricultural research can take different levels and forms. For example, Ashby (1996) identified five types of participation, ranging from ‘nominal’ (farmers’ land and labour are used), through ‘consultative’ (farmers’ opinions are sought), ‘action-oriented’ (farmers are involved in implementation) and ‘decision-making’ (farmers participate in decision making), to ‘collegial participation’ (researchers strengthen farmers’ own research).

Nonetheless, co-innovation, with its perceived potential to privilege tacit (rather than only codified or explicit) knowledge and the different priorities of stakeholders, especially ‘users’¹ such as farmers and foresters (EIP-AGRI SP, 2017), through extensive knowledge sharing currently dominates agricultural innovation policy discourse. For example, the European Innovation Partnership ‘Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability’ (EIP-AGRI), a relatively new approach under the European Union’s (EU) Europe 2020 strategy, aims to ‘speed up’ innovation in agriculture and related sectors in the EU by linking policies, instruments and actors (EIP-AGRI, 2013). The time lags between initial research investment and ultimate impacts on the development and adoption of technological innovations can often be measured in decades (Alston et al., 2008). Projects funded in the frame of the EIP-AGRI are required to be implemented by ‘multi-actor’ partnerships which bring together complementary knowledge and other resources (for example, physical and financial) of different types of actor (farmers, foresters, businesses, academics, NGOs etc.) and to employ the ‘co-innovation’ model. This means that consortium partners are expected to ‘co-create’ new knowledge ‘all along the project’ (i.e. from beginning to end). The co-innovation approach is also strongly supported by international agencies such as FAO (FAO, 2014) and the World Bank (World Bank, 2012).

In order to optimise the use of participatory approaches in agricultural research, Neef and Neubert (2011) stressed the need to move beyond simple linear typologies of participation (such as that of Ashby, 1996), which they found to be insufficiently fine-grained to depict the wide variation of stakeholder participation in their own research programmes. Recognising that stakeholder participation in agricultural research is a multi-dimensional process, they adopted a new approach by developing a participation framework based on (a) project type; (b) research approach; (c) researchers’ characteristics; (d) interaction between researchers and (other) stakeholders; (e) stakeholders’ characteristics and (f) stakeholders’ benefits. The framework was successfully tested and applied in South-East Asia and Africa.

Fielke et al. (2018) developed a conceptual model involving characteristics that help achieve co-innovation outcomes and increase impact. The three structural elements of the model were network-level functions, the structural level and resource functions. The authors correctly pointed out that actors’ resources are finite and that the costs of the co-innovation approach can potentially outweigh the benefits. The time and energy (and other resources) committed to the co-innovation process must be balanced against the expected outcomes and impact. In other words, the process should be as *efficient* as possible, i.e. it should achieve the end goal with minimum waste, effort or energy.

This model utilised the structural-functional analysis of Wieczorek

and Hekkert (2012) to analyse the performance of innovation projects. The four elements that comprise the structural part of this analysis are actors, interactions, institutions and infrastructure. The seven functional components that shape an innovation system’s performance are (a) entrepreneurial activities; (b) knowledge development; (c) knowledge diffusion; (d) guidance of the search (i.e. is there a shared goal); (e) market formation (how big is it, are there barriers); (f) mobilisation of resources and (g) the creation of legitimacy (is the process seen as legitimate). Cronin et al. (2022) also used this structural-functional analysis to identify two categories of ‘multi-level system failures’, which they termed ‘multipliers’ and ‘stackers’, which can pose barriers to the functioning of an innovation system as a result of the interaction and connection between different innovation system levels, plus the presence of mitigating factors.

Co-innovation demands intense communication and collaboration between the different actors in the partnership (and maybe also those in the larger periphery of engaged stakeholders). Thus, the *attitude* of actors in the consortium/partnership towards interaction (with others) is highly relevant to any analysis of how to optimise co-innovation. In this paper we consider the attitude of actors towards interaction within and beyond the multi-actor partnership. This approach is in line with the literature on typologies from other disciplines. For example, both Kluge (2000) and Collier et al. (2012) cite examples of multidimensional typologies in which one dimension reflects the *behaviour* of the subject: delinquent behaviour of adolescents by the former and targeting rewards in electoral mobilisation in the latter.

The novelty of our work lies in the fact that we have analysed the co-innovation activities of a substantial number of multi-actor partnerships in agriculture, forestry and related sectors² from across Europe according to two dimensions. The first of these uses the four structural components of the OIS identified by Van Lancker et al. (2016). The second addresses the prevailing policy context of ‘co-innovation’ and its core principle that interaction and knowledge sharing ‘all along the project’ between actors with a broad range of experience, expertise and other competences serves to optimise the innovation process. In line with Doty and Glick (1994), we show that ‘contextual contingencies’ encountered by multi-actor co-innovation partnerships can result in the adoption of contrasting approaches to implementation. The result is a ‘typology’ composed of a matrix of eight ‘ideal types’ of co-innovation activity.

In the next section, we set out the building blocks of the typology and introduce the data set to which it was applied. Then, the eight ‘types’ of co-innovation activity are described in detail. Following this, we identify the principal first-order constructs in the typology according to the evidence. Finally, we draw some conclusions and recommendations from our analysis.

3. Methodology

3.1. Development of the typology

A typology is an organised system that divides a population into groups based on shared attributes (Collier et al., 2012). These groups or types can be described by a particular constellation of the attributes that form the basis of the typology. Accordingly, every typology is based on an ‘attribute space’ which results from the combination of the selected attributes and their dimensions (Kluge, 2000). The elements within a type should be as similar as possible (internal heterogeneity on the ‘level of the type’) and the differences between the types must be as strong as possible (external heterogeneity on the ‘level of the typology’).

Collier et al. (2012) listed four ‘building blocks’ in the development of a typology. Firstly, the *overarching concept* (or ‘title’) measured by the typology. Secondly, the *row and column variables*. The overarching

¹ We prefer the term ‘user’ to ‘end user’ as it better reflects the farmers’ and foresters’ role in the innovation process.

² By ‘related sectors’, we mean other activities directly involving farmers and/or foresters such as on-farm tourism.

concept is disaggregated into two or more dimensions and the categories of these dimensions provide the core defining attributes of the typology. Thirdly, the *matrix*. Cross-tabulation of the component categories of these dimensions creates a matrix which serves to show the relationships among different components. Fourthly, *cell types*. These are the concepts and associated terms located in the cells. The cell types are ‘a kind of’ in relation to the overarching concept measured by the typology.

The overarching concept or dependent variable measured our typology is ‘effectiveness of co-innovation by a multi-actor partnership’ (in agriculture, forestry and related sectors) (cf. Klerkx et al., 2017). ‘Effectiveness’ may include any aspect(s) that influence either the ‘speed’ of the innovation process, the (efficient) use of resources (e.g. human, physical or financial) and/or its impact. After the methodology of Collier et al. (2012), and the theoretical arguments of Van Lancker et al. (2016) and Fieldsend et al. (2020), and the prevailing policy emphasis on co-innovation that demands constant dialogue between actors, the two dimensions of the overarching concept (i.e. the row and column variables in the typology matrix) are the ‘structural components of the OIS’ and ‘attitude (of actors) towards interaction’. To show the contribution of attitude to optimising co-innovation, two illustrative levels of attitude are used, namely ‘fosters interaction’ and ‘indifferent towards interaction’.³ These can be interpreted as representing the ‘positive end’ and the ‘middle’ of the scale of attitude. It is assumed that any actor with any kind of ‘negative’ attitude towards interaction would not want to participate in an interactive partnership.

The four structural components and the two options for ‘attitude’ result in a 4×2 matrix and eight cells (Fig. 1). Equivalent criteria were used in formulating the cell types (cf. Collier et al., 2012) and each cell was attributed a name that reflects the concept corresponding to it. In the parlance of the typology literature (Doty and Glick, 1994), each cell represents an ‘ideal type’. ‘Ideal’ is used in the sense that the existing variety is concentrated into (and captured by) a limited number of ‘types’ or ‘constructions’ (Kluge, 2000). No one ideal type is intrinsically ‘superior’ to another but may be more ‘appropriate’ in given circumstances.

3.2. Data source

The data gathered from 200 co-innovation partnerships involving farmers and foresters from across Europe form the evidence base for our analysis. The research was conducted in the period May–July 2019 by the 17 partners in the LIAISON consortium and the methodology was described in detail by Fieldsend et al. (2020) and Fieldsend et al. (2021). Most of the 200 partnerships were taken from a compiled database of several thousand such examples drawn from official EU databases. A second source was an EU-wide Rural Innovation Contest (EURIC) held by the LIAISON project which was aimed at identifying less formal examples of co-innovation, especially non-project activities and those based on value chain networks.

Reflecting the emphasis in the LIAISON research on EIP-AGRI related activities in particular, and EU-funded actions more generally, 87 reviews were of H2020 projects and EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OG), and altogether 135 were of projects financed by the EU. However, other project-based and non-project approaches, including formal and informal partnerships, and even activities with no external funding, can foster co-innovation in agriculture, forestry and related sectors. All these ‘share the space’ in the AKIS (Fieldsend et al., 2021). Hence, our analysis is based not only on the results from ‘projects’, but on the insights gathered from the study of a broad range of co-innovation partnerships.

Each review consisted of three phases and the information obtained from each phase was collated into a standard data gathering template. Firstly, desk research drew on published information (such as project

³ These are illustrations of *behaviour* and not of the level of commitment to the co-innovation activity as such.

websites). Secondly, a ‘one telephone call’ semi-structured interview of about 1.5 h duration was conducted with a key informant. Of these, 128 described themselves as being ‘coordinator’, ‘project leader’ or in a comparable role, a further 21 occupied evidently senior positions such as ‘managing director’ and the remaining 51 were ‘project partners’ or similar. Among them, 82 were female, 115 were male and three were not defined. Thirdly, a post-interview reflection by the LIAISON partner looked at keys to the success or otherwise of the co-innovation process.

In line with the OIS concept, the interview was structured to explore how the partnership was formed (the ‘diverse actors’), cooperation within it (the ‘innovation process’), communication with external stakeholders (the ‘innovation network’) and the roles of the institutions. Whereas multiple choice answers were suitable for questions such as ‘Country of residence of the coordinator’, text was the only appropriate format for gathering the required insights into, for example, ‘attitudes’ and ‘group dynamics’. To facilitate subsequent analysis, strict maximum character counts for each question were built into the template, thereby forcing interviewers to be disciplined in the way they summarised the information. The data gathering template was tested in practice before being finalised and shared with the LIAISON partners.

The 200 completed templates were collated into a single spreadsheet for analysis and, with a combined word count in excess of 180,000, proved to be a rich source of material. For each of the four structural components of the OIS, one person was responsible for analysing both the quantitative and qualitative data. For each component, all content pertaining to attitude towards interaction was extracted and used for determining the first-order constructs of the typology, as follows. Firstly, the content was structured according to distinct topics (e.g. ‘motivation for interaction’) and, secondly, examples of contrasting approaches were used to inform the wording of the content of Tables 1–4. Those responsible for collating and analysing the data referred to the interviewers for clarifications whenever necessary.

In section 5 we include quotes from interviewees as examples from our data of the principal first-order constructs. To ensure confidentiality, no projects are referred to by name but only occasionally by their general description, for example “an OG from Germany”. Any quotes from interviewees are not attributed to individuals.

4. Typology of multi-actor co-innovation partnerships

Here we present the concepts that correspond to each of the eight cell types, based on the data from the 200 co-innovation partnerships. The analysis is structured firstly by structural component of the OIS and secondly by actors’ attitude towards interaction.

4.1. The actors

Innovation partnerships can include actors with different ‘labels’, such as firms, research institutes, customers, authorities and financial organisations (Klein Woolthuis et al., 2005). In line with the categorisation of Knotter et al. (2019), the participating organisations in our 200 reviewed partnerships included advisory, business, education, (individual) farmer or forester, public body, processing or marketing SME, processing or marketing producer organisation, research, and organisations representing or supporting practitioner groups (such as farmers’ and foresters’ associations). Their representation, either as a leader/coordinator or as a partner varied according to the type of partnership. For example, research organisations were dominant in (international) H2020 projects while advisory organisations and individual farmers and foresters were very strongly represented in (national) ‘Operational Groups’ (OG) funded in the frame of EIP-AGRI. But a ‘label’ is an imprecise tool for assessing whether the partnership brings together the necessary complementary knowledge, attitudes and other resources (human, physical and financial; see Wieczorek and Hekkert, 2012) to co-innovate. For example, farmers may contribute ‘codified’ as well as ‘tacit’ knowledge to the co-innovation process.

Effectiveness of co-innovation by a multi-actor partnership

		Attitude towards interaction	
		<i>Fosters interaction</i>	<i>Indifferent towards interaction</i>
Structural components of the Organisational Innovation System	<i>The actors</i>	Diverse engagement	Focused effort
	<i>The innovation process</i>	Inclusive community	Structured organisation
	<i>Dissemination and embedding</i>	Open network	Targeted activity
	<i>The enabling environment</i>	Action mobilises support	Self-sufficient venture

Fig. 1. Cross-tabulation matrix of the typology.

An important aspect of actor capacity shown by our research is inclusion in networks: many of the reviewed partnerships were based on a core group of actors that had previously worked together. These core groups are well placed to co-innovate but may exclude less well-connected actors, such as those from certain groups or geographical regions, that may have unique capacities. Other actor capacities (or lack of them) that can influence attitudes towards interaction include language skills and familiarity with the process. Based on actor capacity, two ideal types in our typology can be identified (Table 1).

4.2. The innovation process

Since the co-innovation process involves frequent iteration and feedback to adjust to unforeseen developments and correct mistakes (Wielinga et al., 2008), there should be ample opportunities for the various partners to contribute to the process ‘all along the project’. In around 90% of the reviewed partnerships, some or all of the partners were involved in setting and defining the targets and objectives to a great or some extent. On the other hand, not all actors will make an equal contribution to the co-innovation process at every stage of the activity. Sometimes a core group had a dominating influence. In any case, at any point in the process, some forms of expertise (and other resources) will be more apposite than others, even if there is still merit in this expertise being challenged by other actors in the partnership.

Among the reviewed projects, most H2020 consortia included 20 or more partners whereas many projects funded from other sources involved ten partners or fewer. However, especially among non-project activities such as clusters and networks, which may be of indeterminate timescale and open to actors (organisations or individuals) joining or leaving at any time during their existence, the number of partners could be difficult to determine. International partnerships by definition have a much wider geographical distribution of actors than national or local ones. Partnership size, geographical distribution and duration all influenced the form of the co-innovation process adopted by the partnership, including form and frequency of communication, as well as use of language.

Finally, some partnerships adopted more formal ways of working than others. Based on all these considerations, we characterise two ideal types in the typology (Table 2).

4.3. Dissemination and embedding

Chesbrough (2003, p.38) noted that a principle of the open innovation paradigm is that “not all of the smart people work for us” and that this premise legitimates the acceptance of ideas that were ‘not invented here’. If a multi-actor co-innovation partnership is the core of an OIS, then it can be argued that ‘opening up’ the partnership to external

knowledge and ideas, especially from a larger periphery of engaged stakeholders, can contribute to optimising innovation. More than 20 of our 50 reviewed H2020 projects set up ‘practice-led innovation networks’, ‘farmer innovation groups’ or similar structures to foster co-innovation between the core group and the larger periphery. But examples of all types of reviewed partnerships adopted ‘outreach’ practices, including ‘farmer (discussion) groups’, ‘clusters’, ‘co-creation sessions’, ‘commonage groups’, ‘joint action teams’, ‘ambassadors for innovation and technology’ and ‘pilot innovation environments’. However, it is unlikely that ‘more consultation is better’ in every instance and such activities were relatively rare among our reviewed OGS. Furthermore, for non-project activities (such as networks) that did not involve formal consortia it was sometimes difficult to identify a dividing line between the ‘core group’ and the larger periphery.

The innovation topic (including confidentiality issues), as well as the profile both of the actors (some of which were organisations with large memberships) in the partnership and the external stakeholders, influenced the ways in which the partnership engaged with the larger periphery, including the location of engagement and type of outputs. From all these insights, two ideal types can be identified (Table 3) and, as with the other three structural components of the OIS, we do not claim that one is superior to the other.

4.4. The enabling environment

Co-innovation partnerships cannot operate independently of the enabling environment as this constrains behaviour and regulates interaction (Coenen and Díaz López, 2010; Klerkx et al., 2017). But actors have some flexibility in terms of the extent to which they engage with it and, crucially, aspire to mobilise its resources to optimise co-innovation. Optimisation might best be achieved through interacting with the enabling environment or (to the extent possible) being ‘indifferent’ to it. For example, a grant may provide the partnership with the financial resources it needs to innovate and most of our reviewed partnerships received external funding and complied with the associated rules. However, some partnerships were ‘indifferent’ to (i.e. did not use) this opportunity and therefore potentially optimised innovation by avoiding constraints on, for example, eligibility of partners and/or activities, and opportunities for commercialisation.

The reviewed partnerships were drawn from across Europe and therefore encountered varying capacities of (programme) administrators and political stability. They could try to work with (and indeed even improve) these administrative structures or operate independently of them, to the extent possible. Some partnerships made use of tools such as consortium agreements or agreements regulating intellectual property rights (IPR) to provide actors with the necessary reassurance to participate in the co-innovation process and share novel ideas. For others,

Table 1
The actors: first-order constructs of the ideal types ‘diverse engagement’ and ‘focused effort’.

Construct	Ideal type ‘diverse engagement’	Ideal type ‘focused effort’
	<i>The capacities of this ideal type of actor empower them to maximise the extent of their involvement in co-innovation partnerships.</i>	<i>The capacities of this ideal type of actor require them to maximise the return on their involvement in co-innovation partnerships through targeted participation.</i>
Willingness to interact	High level of willingness driven by factors such as enthusiasm, pride in achievement and positive previous experiences of cooperation, for example in earlier projects. This willingness may extend to participating in a broad range of co-innovation topics and/or with a wide variety of actors (including those outside their ‘comfort zone’), to leading the partnership and/or designing the programme of activities.	Limited level of willingness caused by factors such as unsatisfactory previous experiences of cooperation. The actor does not aspire to lead a partnership and will only consider participation in innovation activities of exceptional interest.
Motivation for interaction	The primary motivation is ‘autonomous’, for example driven by the desire to find a solution to a problem.	The primary motivation is ‘controlled’, for example driven by financial reward, such as receipt of project funding or the near certainty of a marketable product.
Perceived value of interaction	The actor sees themselves as a participant in a collective activity in which genuine cooperation will lead to results of value to a wide range of users. Interaction may continue even after the initial result has been achieved.	The actor participates in the collective activity in the expectation of them producing results (such as new knowledge) from which they can directly benefit. The interaction ends once the result has been achieved.
Approach to self-assessment	The main evaluation criterion is the extent to which the problem is solved.	Evaluation criteria include, for example, number of scientific papers published.
Conceptual understanding	The actor has a good understanding of the principles of co-innovation which underpins their effective contribution to the work of a partnership.	The actor’s understanding of the principles of co-innovation is weak, which may limit the value of their contribution to the partnership, and they are dependent upon the advice of other actors in the partnership.
Degree of network inclusion	Long-established and active involvement in networks that are extensive in terms of, for example, geographical distribution and complementary knowledge.	Limited involvement in terms of duration and/or the size and/or the diversity of the actor’s network.
Formality of network inclusion	A partner in formal (common interest) networks that are intended to be well placed to initiate co-innovation activities, for example by attracting commercial funding.	Not included in any formal (common interest) networks and therefore effectively excluded from many potential co-innovation activities.
Familiarity with the process	Extensive previous participation in co-innovation partnerships means that the actor has the capacity to design effective programmes of activities (for example, ensuring dissemination and embedding) and/or secure financial support.	Lack of previous participation in co-innovation partnerships means that the capacity of the actor to design programmes of activities and/or secure financial support is low or confined to very few topics, localities or funding sources.
‘Track record’ of interaction	Wide experience of participating in multi-actor co-innovation activities (with a diverse range of partners) can	Limited experience of participation in multi-actor co-innovation activities means that both the internal

Table 1 (continued)

Construct	Ideal type ‘diverse engagement’	Ideal type ‘focused effort’
	instil an internalised belief in the value of the co-innovation approach and reinforce the reputation of the actor as a valuable and reliable partner (or indeed as the leader of a partnership).	belief in the value of the co-innovation approach and the reputation of the actor as a valuable partner are weak.
Availability of resources	Existence of sufficient workforce of the required calibre and adequate infrastructure (such as farmland or forested area) means that (a) the actor has the necessary resources to contribute to a co-innovation partnership and/or (b) their resources are in demand by potential partners seeking to complement their own capabilities.	Workforce or infrastructure limitations mean that (a) the actor has restricted capacity to contribute to a co-innovation partnership and/or (b) their resources are of only limited interest to potential partners.
Language skills	Good language skills allow participation in international partnerships.	Extent of language skills limits participation to national and/or sub-national partnerships.
Gender inclusion	There is a deliberate intention to ensure gender balance and inclusion of representatives of disadvantaged groups in the workgroup.	Participation in the workgroup is determined solely on merit (e.g. skills).

especially among very small partnerships, the absence of formal agreements contributed to minimising the administrative burden. Some employed innovation brokers although most did not. Once again, therefore, we can characterise two ideal types in the typology (Table 4).

5. The principal first-order constructs in co-innovation

The relative importance of the first-order constructs used to describe the ideal types can be estimated by ‘expert raters’ (Doty and Glick, 1994). In this section, we attempt to identify the most important issues per structural component of the OIS using our insights from the analysis of the 200 reviewed partnerships.

5.1. The actors

Knowledge is the foundation of an organisation’s competitive advantage, but this knowledge resides within the individuals it employs. Thus, *willingness to interact* and *motivation for interaction* at both the individual and ‘corporate’ level are important issues concerning knowledge sharing. Fogg (2009) argued that human behaviour is a product of three factors: motivation, ability and triggers. An intrinsic willingness (and ability) to interact needs to be present but knowledge sharing will not occur without a trigger and motivation. Two types of motivation are described in the literature (Dato Mansor et al., 2015). Autonomous motivation means engaging in an activity volitionally, for example pursuing an activity out of interest and because it is enjoyable (intrinsic motivation), and because it is personally meaningful and fits one’s value system (identified regulation). Controlled motivation means engaging in an activity out of pressure that can come from outside sources, such as promised rewards and threats of punishment (external regulation), or inside sources, such as when one’s self esteem is contingent upon successfully completing a task (introjected regulation).

For many of our reviewed partnerships, the trigger was the identification of a problem which could potentially be solved by multi-actor cooperation. This often motivated one actor to invite others to form a partnership, or to resurrect or prolong a partnership to address the issue, in other words the motivation was *autonomous*. An interviewee from

Table 2

The co-innovation process: first-order constructs of the ideal types ‘inclusive community’ and ‘structured organisation’.

Construct	Ideal type ‘inclusive community’	Ideal type ‘structured organisation’
	<i>This ideal type of partnership features informal structures and inclusion of all partners in the organisational arrangements it adopts to maximise its capacity to optimise co-innovation.</i>	<i>This ideal type of partnership features formal structures and an emphasis on clear management in the organisational arrangements it adopts to maximise its capacity to optimise co-innovation.</i>
Duration	The co-innovation activity has an indeterminate time schedule. This tends to be a feature of networks and ‘bottom-up’ innovation partnerships without external funding.	The activity is designed to be completed in a fixed term. This is a feature of projects and a requirement frequently imposed by funding programmes.
Setting of objectives and targets	Project objectives and targets are discussed collectively among all partners and defined and set based on consensus. This may be a lengthy process in order to achieve a clear vision that is shared by all.	Co-innovation objectives and targets are defined by the lead partner or a core team of partners, resulting in a clear vision shared by the most senior actors in the partnership.
Formality of work plan	Informal and/or general and/or indeterminate plan of activities that is (potentially) responsive to changing circumstances (even if the overall goals and objectives remain unchanged), including the emergence of important information that was not available at the beginning of the process.	Formal and/or detailed and/or structured set of activities with clearly defined expected outputs, as often required in projects and by funding programmes. Any (significant) revisions require compliance with an (internal or external) approvals procedure before implementation.
Focus of work plan	The work plan is organised around practical activities or events.	The work plan is organised around work packages (or equivalent).
Structure of work plan	Although there is a clear set of objectives for the innovation activity as a whole, partners develop their own sub-objectives for their programme of work.	There is a clear set of objectives for the co-innovation activity as a whole; but specific partners are responsible for defined sub-objectives (e.g. work packages) of this programme of work.
Distribution of responsibilities	Roles, tasks and responsibilities are shared as widely as possible between some or all partners and are not necessarily clearly defined.	Roles, tasks and responsibilities clearly and discretely distributed among partners according to their skills, resources, interests or other criteria.
Distribution of workload	Partners make a balanced contribution to the workload of the co-innovation activity.	Core partners undertake most of the work in the co-innovation activity.
Hierarchy in the partnership	All partners are equal. Decision making is undertaken collectively, and individual partners take the lead only on a short-term basis to deliver a specific innovation activity.	There is a designated consortium/partnership leader and/or a core team of partners that take the lead both in decision making and managing the co-innovation activities. The relative seniority of partners may vary over the course of the co-innovation activity, according to circumstances.
Degree of knowledge and information sharing	As much knowledge and information as possible is shared among all partners; procedures for sharing are informal.	Knowledge and information are shared between partners on a ‘need to know’ basis, minimising the risk of information overload, and according to formal procedures.

Table 2 (continued)

Construct	Ideal type ‘inclusive community’	Ideal type ‘structured organisation’
Frequency of communication	Communication among all partners occurs regularly and/or frequently.	Communication among all partners occurs only when necessary, because sometimes there is nothing new to share.
Form of communication	Communication mostly takes place through physical meetings, including (where appropriate) field visits. This approach is most feasible with small, local partnerships.	Communication predominantly occurs electronically (email, Zoom etc.). This is essential in the case of partnerships that are large and/or geographically dispersed.
Language of communication	Use of language within the partnership (as opposed to in dissemination activities) reflects the needs of the partners. In small, local partnerships only one language may be necessary. In larger, dispersed partnerships, communication in several languages may be necessary to maximise inclusion, for example of practitioner partners.	Communication within the partnership takes place in one language only, thereby minimising administrative and possibly cost burdens.

Spain gave an example: “*The project was set up because there was a need to improve the efficiency and performance on the extraction and processing of olive oil. To get this project started a group of organisations formed to take the first steps*”. On other occasions, the trigger was the publication of a call for (project) proposals accompanied by co-financing. Here the motivation was *controlled* because it involved a ‘promised reward’ (i.e. money). A representative of a H2020 project stated “*The project arose from a specific call entitled ... that was launched under the H2020 programme. The consortium was specifically constructed to prepare a proposal for this call*”. It should not be assumed that the former is ‘better’ than the latter. Many projects funded by EU Framework Programmes, for example, have yielded outstanding results when the primary motivation of the participants was controlled.

Various aspects of *network inclusion* are another important feature of the ideal types in the typology. The extent of interlinking between actors and projects was clearly illustrated by the results of the 200 reviews, reflecting the findings of Manning (2010) on the institutional embeddedness of network agency. Many interviewees stated that the current project was developed from an earlier one, and frequently this earlier project was delivered by a partnership drawn from the same network. In the case of a LIFE project “*All partners but one (three out of four) knew each other from a previous project and wanted to continue the good cooperation with a follow-up project on climate change adaptation*”.

Inclusion of a wide diversity of actors in a network can be beneficial, both for the network and for the actors concerned. However, not all actors have similar inclusion in networks. Owing to circumstances (such as negative previous experiences, digital divide, age and/or farm type), some actors (farmers) are ‘harder to reach’ than others (Hurley et al., 2022). OGs may be built on limited networks. An interviewee from a French OG explained that “*The idea to make a project that would meet the needs and expectations of farmers in the area and to have a rapid implementation was born from an interaction between the Chamber of Agriculture and an association of local farmers. The search for more partners was then carried out by mobilising different networks*”. Cofré-Bravo et al. (2019) showed that farmers exploit bonding, bridging and linking social capital to compose their networks and that the balance between the three types is based on their personal motivations, innovation objectives and social endowments.

Table 3
Dissemination and embedding: first-order constructs of the ideal types ‘open network’ and ‘targeted activity’.

Construct	Ideal type ‘open network’	Ideal type ‘targeted activity’
Setting objectives	<i>This ideal type of partnership adopts the following approaches to maximising engagement with other actors in the AKIS in order to optimise co-innovation.</i> During the design phase, exercises such as market research and exploring consumer demands are carried out in consultation with stakeholders with a view to validating the practicality of the planned activities and focusing them on users’ needs.	<i>This ideal type of partnership places more emphasis on internal co-innovation and adopts the following alternative approaches to engaging with other actors in the AKIS.</i> The practicalities and relevance of the planned activities are already known (e.g. through experience or the nature of the topic) and no pre-consultation is necessary.
Checking results	External stakeholders are asked to check certain results arising from the work of the co-innovation partnership.	This does not occur, for example owing to confidentiality issues.
Partnership competence	Limitations in the collective competence of the partnership make continuous interaction with external stakeholders desirable or even essential. The existence of any limitations will be determined by factors such as the complexity of the topic. Examples include gaps in expertise or geographical representation and can occur for various reasons. For example, budgetary limitations imposed by funding programmes may preclude the inclusion of all desired participants in the partnership, or it may only become apparent later that some expertise is missing from the partnership.	The partnership includes all necessary competences (whether it be, for example, either very many partners with a wide range of expertise, or a narrow geographical distribution owing to the limited topicality of the work) and no external input is needed to fill any gaps.
Partner networks	The partnership does not include organisations with extensive networks (e.g. farmers’ organisations) and is therefore obliged to disseminate its outputs and gather feedback by engaging with stakeholders through formal activities, for example by setting up platforms or networks.	The partnership includes organisations with extensive networks through which outputs can routinely be disseminated and feedback gathered in passive ways (i.e. through partners’ existing communication channels and informal interaction) without the need for formal activities.
Inclusion of individuals	The partnership is composed only of a limited number of organisations and no persons in an individual capacity. Engagement with stakeholders is necessary to achieve ‘mass’ dissemination or consultation/feedback.	The partnership includes many individual participants. This is commonly the case in value chain networks. With so many participants within the co-innovation activity, there may be less need to engage with outside actors.
Quality of engagement	The partnership establishes long-term participatory structures to involve stakeholders, thereby maximising potential for feedback.	Only ‘ad hoc’ engagement with stakeholders (for example, occasional workshops and conferences) is justified.
Breadth of engagement	The partnership interacts with a broad range of actors, communicates in several languages, and/or with ‘harder-to-reach’ or disadvantaged groups such as	The topic of the co-innovation activity does not merit any special effort to engage with a broad range of actors, in several languages and/or with hard-to-reach or

Table 3 (continued)

Construct	Ideal type ‘open network’	Ideal type ‘targeted activity’
	smallholder farmers, women farmers and farmers in remote areas. These actions may be an obligation of any funding programme or a consequence of the co-innovation topic.	disadvantaged groups, thereby saving on resources, for example for making translations.
Location of engagement	Great importance is attached to holding meetings in the demonstration field rather than the classroom to improve communication between the partnership and practice stakeholders.	No special emphasis is placed on choice of location as this is not relevant to the topic of the co-innovation activity.
Duration of engagement	Stakeholders are engaged throughout the entire period of the co-innovation activity.	It is only necessary to engage with stakeholders at certain stages of the co-innovation activity, such as towards the end during a scaling-up phase.
Participation in educational activities	The partners take part in educational activities to share their ideas and results with a future generation of potential co-innovators.	Such participation is not of any value or is ruled out for reasons of confidentiality.
Links with other projects or activities	The partnership has links to other former and/or ongoing projects or other co-innovation activities, and may engage in joint research/development, sharing data and results, and/or dissemination/consultation activities with them.	Links with other projects are very limited or are not necessary and would therefore be a drain on resources, or are undesirable, for example for reasons of confidentiality.
Funding of co-innovation activities	The partnership funds co-innovation activities by stakeholders, for example in the form of sub-projects.	Such activities are not funded by the partnership.
Type of outputs	The partnership develops practical tools (e.g. software) that can be used by stakeholders, even after the end of the project.	Outputs are primarily in the form of documents such as ‘deliverables’ or ‘practice abstracts’.
Follow-up activities	Stakeholder engagement continues after the co-innovation activity has ended (possibly in connection with setting up a new one), and the results of the activity remain available to them.	No follow-up activities are deemed to be necessary.

Maintaining a smaller network, as in ideal type ‘focused effort’, is not necessarily a negative approach. Actors, whether organisations or individuals, may wish to devote their potentially limited capacity (associated with *availability of resources*) to activities of most interest to them. The problem arises when exclusion is a consequence of ‘path dependency’. Many organisations in the older EU Member States have both a ‘*track-record of interaction and familiarity with the process*’ of participating in co-innovation partnerships (Fieldsend et al., 2020). It can be difficult for actors from newer EU Member States to gain access to these long-established networks and this can limit the capacity of networks to identify and nurture potential new ideas. During consortium formation, a H2020 project interviewee reported “Organisations brought on board to answer a call that involved multi-actor organisations and engaged directly with farmers were readily available in Northern Europe, existed but not as known to partners in Eastern Europe and hard to find / not known to partners in Southern Europe”. Furthermore, funding resources are limited: Fotheringham et al. (2016) pointed out that the EIP-AGRI has the capacity to involve only a very small percentage of all the farmers in the EU.

Conceptual understanding among actors of the principles of co-

Table 4
The enabling environment: first-order constructs of the ideal types ‘action mobilises support’ and ‘self-sufficient venture’.

Construct	Ideal type ‘action mobilises support’	Ideal type ‘self-sufficient venture’
	<i>Specific factors of the enabling environment induce certain responses from this ideal type of partnership which are intended to contribute to optimising co-innovation.</i>	<i>Specific factors of the enabling environment induce alternative responses (or, in some instances, non-responses) from this ideal type of partnership which are also intended to contribute to optimising co-innovation.</i>
Availability of financial support	A call for proposals may be the trigger for the co-innovation activity. Alternatively, the idea for co-innovation may occur first and a source of funding sought to ‘operationalise’ the activity. Partnerships may secure different types of funding for contrasting activities on separate occasions, or a mix of funding to support a particular activity.	Co-innovation partnerships which are privately funded and/or the actors already have the required financial resources have no need to interact with funding programmes.
Administrative basis of the partnership	A consortium agreement or equivalent legal or paralegal framework is in place. This is frequently a requirement imposed by funding programmes.	The co-innovation activity is not covered by a consortium agreement or any other kind of legal or paralegal framework. This tends to be a feature of networks, small partnerships and ‘bottom-up’ innovation partnerships without external funding.
Intellectual property rights (IPR)	IPR arrangements are put in place to give partnership actors the necessary reassurance that they can share novel ideas and work openly and honestly together.	Partners consider IPR arrangements to be unnecessary, for example when the nature of the innovation is less exclusive, the benefits can be shared appropriately, and/or they have more trust in each other.
Non-EU regulations	When the consortium includes partners from non-EU (especially non-European) countries, different laws and regulations come into play which are not harmonised with the EU regulations. To bridge the gap, partners engage in bilateral discussions and agreements.	Partnerships that do not intend to involve actors from non-EU Member States in their activities are ‘indifferent’ to this issue.
Innovation brokers	Actors consider it to be beneficial and/or essential to seek external help in identifying additional partners, writing the proposal and/or clarifying (funding programme) rules and are willing to devote financial resources to secure this help.	The partnership considers that it has the necessary competences to perform all the required activities and/or is unwilling to devote financial resources to paying for external help.
Trust	The social environment of the partnership lacks social capital/trust, so it is necessary to spend the required amount of time and effort to build it between the partners.	The level of trust is already sufficient in the partners’ social environment (higher level of social capital), much reducing the need to develop it.
External administrative limitations	Weak capacity of (programme) administrators (especially evident in certain regions/countries), requires	Co-innovation partnerships do not develop compensating activities since the administrative

Table 4 (continued)

Construct	Ideal type ‘action mobilises support’	Ideal type ‘self-sufficient venture’
	the partnership to spend more time on planning and building ‘bypasses’ to allow the co-innovation process to proceed. The partnership might aim to influence the system/policy to mitigate or eliminate administrative burdens.	mechanisms in the territory or operating environment are efficient and effective.
Culture of participation	In situations where there is a weak culture of participation which can limit interactivity among actors and stakeholders, the partnership seeks to reduce the impact by developing clear views on shared benefits as well as building trust.	In cases/countries/regions where actors are ready to cooperate and share their opinions, a partnership can be ‘indifferent’ to this factor.
Political (in) stability	Political instability requires the co-innovation partnership to be resilient and to develop skills and procedures to mitigate the impacts of changes.	Co-innovation partnerships operating in territories with a stable political environment and where continuity is assured do not need to consider this issue.
Weather conditions	Where unpredictable weather conditions may cause delays in experiments, co-innovation partnerships need to carry out preliminary risk assessments and wise planning to mitigate the impacts.	Partnerships can disregard this issue if it has no relevance to or likely impact on their co-innovation activities.

innovation is a topic whose importance is probably greatly overlooked and understated. It is not enough for a partnership to be ‘multi-actor’; the partners must recognise that, to be successful, the co-innovation activity they design and implement demands knowledge and other resource sharing ‘all along the project’. Although the concept is well established, it is still not correctly understood and implemented by many actors in the AKIS (EU SCAR AKIS, 2019).

5.2. The innovation process

An important aspect of the reviewed co-innovation activities is their duration. The primary distinction among them was between ‘projects’, which inter alia normally have a fixed term, and other ‘actor configurations’, including long-term cooperation networks. If the fixed-term nature of the project approach has the potential to be a weakness, it is often addressed by partnerships and networks of actors perpetuating themselves to secure follow-up funding, an example being the H2020 project NEFERTITI, which is the successor to the projects PLAID and AgriDemo-F2F. But the (fixed term) ‘project’ is not the only means of co-innovation in agriculture, forestry and related sectors. A Norwegian interviewee reported “The project started as a value chain cooperation and then we established a formal partnership. Then we saw that we were ready for the next step, and we applied for more money”. In terms of innovation in the AKIS, therefore, this prompts the question, where does the ‘project’ end and the ‘network’ start? Cronin et al. (2021) identified four types of configurations: projects, programmes, clusters/networks/cooperatives and single entrepreneur initiatives. To this list can be added value chain networks (Manley, 2003). Many of the non-EU funded partnerships in our dataset were not ‘projects’ and indeed projects cannot be the sole focus of co-innovation research.

Co-innovation is a complex process based on social interaction and collective decision making, and several factors are important in determining its success. The first of these concerns setting of objectives and targets, which follows on from the initial identification of the problem

that (frequently) precedes the formation of the partnership. Collective setting of objectives and targets is central to the idea of multi-actor cooperation (EU SCAR AKIS, 2019) but can take different forms. In a Dutch OG “Everyone was involved [in setting the targets and objectives] because everyone shared a strong objective”. By contrast, for a privately-funded project in Romania, “The core proposal was drafted by the coordinator, but partners were consulted on specific elements ... with many ideas collected from farmers and assimilated into the proposal”.

The topics of degree of knowledge sharing, and frequency, form and language of communication were frequently mentioned during our interviews. Our interviewees strongly emphasised the importance of equality between the partners in terms of recognising the value of their complementary knowledge but there were instances where interviewees felt that their potential and/or contribution was undervalued. For example, an interviewee from an Interreg Europe project reported “Eastern European partners were somehow in a ‘wait and see’ position with Western Europeans in terms of decision making”. Cronin et al. (2022) listed three factors that can mitigate ‘openness failure’ in H2020 partnerships. Firstly, coordinators and partners who have experience in working in multi-actor settings are willing and able to work across disciplines and are engaged, enthusiastic and motivated. Secondly, a positive working environment with clear aims and transparent communication. Thirdly, working on a topic that receives policy attention creates a higher purpose for the joint work and motivates engagement.

Concerning the focus and structure of the work plan, a representative of a H2020 project stated “A detailed work plan was elaborated which stated clearly the work division. The work plan was carried out when all partners agreed on it”. But our more diverse range of reviewed partnerships are not necessarily constrained by the ‘rules’ of H2020 such as fixed terms and budgets, defined consortia and detailed workplans. In a Belgian Rural Development Programme funded project (i.e. EU funding), “Since the partnership was very small with very distinctive roles, no formal agreements [concerning the division of work between partners] were deemed necessary, to minimise administrative burden”. Similarly, in many partnerships, maximising each partner’s contribution does not necessarily require an even hierarchy in the partnership or an equal distribution of workload or responsibilities among the partners. Differences between partners in resources, interests and competences will determine the optimal arrangements for these issues in the partnership. In a privately-funded project in the UK, for example, “The division of the work came naturally as the partners have specific skills”.

Thus, while it might be anticipated that ‘indifference towards interaction’, for example within a consortium by opting to confine decision making to a core group of partners rather than adopting a genuinely inclusive approach, may slow down innovation, our typology does not attempt to demonstrate such a causal relationship. It may be that confining decision making to a core group maximises its efficiency and speeds up innovation. Whereas a small partnership with a narrow geographical distribution and a limited budget may be able to involve all partners in decision making, in other instances, such as a H2020 project consortium that include 25 or more partners from across the EU and beyond, a more centralised approach to (day-to-day) decision making may be a practical necessity.

5.3. Dissemination and embedding

Of our 200 interviewees, 138 agreed that dialogue with external stakeholders ‘all along the project’ was very important (Fieldsend et al., 2020). For example, a North Sea Region Interreg 5A project representative observed: “We need the stakeholders to contribute in the co-creation. Afterwards we need the farmers to get started with the new business models”. Potential users of an innovation must believe in the product in order to use it and this trust can be gained by ensuring their involvement in setting objectives at the beginning of the innovation process.

The duration and quality of engagement are arguably the most important factors in determining how dissemination and embedding

contributes to optimising innovation. As already indicated, many of our reviewed partnerships set up long-term participatory structures, not just to disseminate results, but also to cultivate feedback that will help with the further development of the co-innovation activity and/or to adapt the innovation(s) to the demands of the external environment. These arrangements can sometimes be quite complex. An interviewee explained how their H2020 project team “facilitated 19 networks including farmers, processors, veterinarians, technical advisors, market representatives and researchers. These networks worked collaboratively to find solutions for important husbandry challenges. The project encouraged a move away from the traditional model of science providing solutions for practice towards a partnership approach where expertise from science and practice were valued more equally. Facilitators supported the networks through six critical steps: problem identification, generation of ideas, planning, small scale trials, implementation and sharing with others”. Continuous dialogue with stakeholders now seems to be well established, but it has perhaps received inadequate attention regarding evaluation of (EU) project proposals. While our typology cautions us that any evaluation guidelines cannot be too prescriptive, as there will be instances where extensive engagement is not appropriate (for example for security or other reasons of confidentiality), it is increasingly accepted as an essential component of the multi-actor approach (EU SCAR AKIS, 2019).

It is normally not enough for a partnership to adopt a ‘one size fits all’ approach to stakeholder engagement. The LIAISON project, for example, maximised its breadth of engagement through several independent actions. Fifteen ‘Rural Innovation Ambassadors’, innovation practitioners identified through the EURIC, were encouraged to be a ‘disruptive influence’ on the work of the consortium. The project partners formulated several theories concerning co-innovation, including this typology, and the Ambassadors were expected to challenge these theories in the light of their practical experience. In the frame of LIAISON work package 6, four ‘macro-regional hubs’ composed of a range of stakeholders were set up at the beginning of the project. The participants were expected to question the extent to which possible EU-wide approaches to optimising co-innovation are applicable to their local circumstances. LIAISON consortium colleagues regularly participated in meetings of the SCAR-AKIS Strategic Working Group. This is a forum in which EU-, national- and regional-level policy makers co-create interventions designed to improve the functioning of the AKIS (EU SCAR AKIS, 2019). It was important for LIAISON to maintain its awareness of policy developments, but it increasingly contributed to them as well. Several LIAISON partners also have connections with academia, such as working with PhD students who represent the next generation of co-innovators. These are all examples of what LIAISON called ‘outreach’ activities that took place alongside conventional ‘dissemination’ of project results.

The inclusion of actors in the innovation partnership with their own partner networks, notably farmers’ and foresters’ organisations, creates a ‘short cut’ through which engagement with very many relevant stakeholders, who will be favourably disposed to accepting the project outputs, can take place. An association of more than 300 wine producers in the Alentejo region of Portugal conducts research on sustainable production for the benefit of its members. The interviewee stated that “The next big step is to have enough critical mass (more than 60% of the economic agents of the Alentejo) to convert this free and voluntary project into a free and mandatory project”.

Several of our interviewees also emphasised sharing of knowledge and dissemination as the next step after project closure, indicating the importance of conducting follow-up activities. An interviewee from an H2020 project on pest management stated “Use of the Twitter account continues beyond the project since it is important to communicate to the potential early adopters”. By contrast, others admitted that, for various reasons, especially lack of funding, no follow-up activities were planned after the end of their project.

Partnerships maintaining links with other projects or actions is also very important. This is quite distinct from individual actors maintaining their own networks. These other projects are also actively innovating,

and links between them have the potential to optimise the process. Such links are increasingly encouraged between projects in the frame of EIP-AGRI (H2020 projects and EIP-AGRI OGs) but can also occur elsewhere in the AKIS.

5.4. The enabling environment

Regarding co-innovation, the ‘soft’ issue of *culture of participation* is a very important part of the enabling environment, because clear differences in culture of participation exist across the EU. In post-socialist EU Member States, there is a reluctance among some actors to join co-operatives or other partnerships, which is reputed to be associated with memories of forced collectivisation (Gijssels and Bussels, 2014). It would be simplistic however to assume that there is only an east-west divide: cultural issues hampering actor participation in co-innovation partnerships have also been identified in Mediterranean areas of Europe (von Münchhausen et al., 2019). In such regions, motivation may have to be boosted through the application of other incentives.

All but a few of our reviewed partnerships benefited from external funding. Another very important issue, therefore, is *availability of financial support*. Funding programmes are a ‘hard’ institution (a ‘rule of the game’) that can trigger or increase the motivation of actors to identify a solution to the problem through partnerships (Cronin et al., 2021). Undoubtedly, as discussed earlier, there are many instances where for at least some actors the primary motivation to participate in a co-innovation activity is the funding, and for them the outputs of this activity are a secondary consideration. Securing financial support for a co-innovation activity frequently imposes obligations on the partnership, such as the need to comply with external monitoring and evaluation rules. This is an example of a situation in which, in terms of compliance, the partnership cannot exercise a choice on whether to ‘mobilise support’ or be ‘self-sufficient’. The only option is to comply with these rules.

Several interviewees gave examples of how funding programme rules affected their co-innovation activity. A representative of an Austrian OG expressed the view that “*Research partners should have been consortium partners, but they are only external partners because of the funding guidelines*”. In an Italian-French Interreg 5A project “*A maximum of eight partners was allowed. For this reason, some actors could not be included in the partnership*”. An interviewee from an H2020 project explained that “*In the call [for proposals], the key stakeholder group to interact with was farmers, so there was a real challenge as to how to administratively engage with them. We wanted to find a way to remunerate farmers from the budget [without them having to be consortium partners], but it was difficult because we could only subcontract and the European Commission does not particularly favour that approach*”.

Our typology makes a distinction between those co-innovation partnerships that ‘foster interaction’ with *innovation brokers* and those that do not (i.e. are ‘indifferent’ to them). Klein Woolthuis et al. (2005) would argue that innovation brokers should be referred to as ‘missing actors’ and cannot be regarded as systemic failures on the ‘rules’ side (i.e. part of the enabling environment). This is a valid point, but support for innovation brokers and innovation brokering is a key aspect of EU agricultural innovation policy (EIP-AGRI, 2013) meaning that innovation brokering has become a ‘rule’ rather than an ‘actor’. Innovation brokers were not widely used among our reviewed co-innovation partnerships (Fieldsend et al., 2020), although interviewees reported positive experiences with them. A Dutch OG declined to use one because, according to the interviewee, “*Another broker would have been too expensive*”.

By contrast, *unpredictable weather conditions*, although mentioned by our interviewees, cannot strictly be defined as an ‘institution’, but is included here as another illustration of the differences in the enabling environment encountered by actors across the EU. Unpredictable weather conditions may cause delays in experiments and in doing so delay the innovation process. The problem can be mitigated (but not

eliminated) with risk assessment and wise planning. BioEast, the Central Eastern European Initiative for Knowledge-based Agriculture, Aquaculture and Forestry in the Bioeconomy (Juhász, 2016), is a government initiative that is attempting to raise the priorities given to topics particularly affecting Central and Eastern Europe such as the impact of climate disruption on continental climates.

Similarly, the ‘hard’ issue of *administrative limitations* is more important in some parts of the EU than in others. An interviewee from a Bulgarian-Swiss project recounted that “*The implementation of the project [in Bulgaria] took place in an unstable political environment – two presidents, 4–5 governments, two chief prosecutors. This made it difficult to communicate with the ministries in connection with changes in the relevant legislation – the communication stopped and started again*”. These big differences in the enabling environment between regions, whether it be the weather or the ‘hard’ (e.g. regulations) or ‘soft’ (e.g. attitudes) ‘rules’, means that it is necessary to recognise the fact that not all regional innovation systems⁴ in the EU perform similarly.

When asked “*How do you evaluate the role of the policy environment in the success of your project?*” interviewees’ answers ranged from “*not important*” to “*very important*”, to some extent dependent on the topic. One interviewee recounted that their H2020 project “*had some problems related with GDPR. It creates a negative environment because some companies are afraid of sharing information (ownership, data management)*”.

Finally, partnerships can ‘optimise innovation’ by ‘interacting’ with the enabling environment in two directions. They may be more ‘successful’ (i.e. the innovation process may be ‘optimised’) by exploiting the enabling environment to the extent possible, for example by securing external funding. However, they can also aspire to modify the ‘rules’ to make them more favourable to optimising innovation. This is especially applicable to, but not confined to, projects whose focus is to make policy recommendations, such as LIAISON.

6. Discussion and conclusion

6.1. Critical reflections on interaction and co-innovation

Neef and Neubert (2011) noted that many frameworks of participation in agricultural research adhere to a linear typology of participatory research with an inherent claim of “the more participation, the better”. However, such typologies have proved to be inadequate, not least because participation may be dynamic in time, depending on the stage of the innovation process (Van Lancker et al., 2016). Neef and Neubert (2011) therefore argued that, rather than *maximising* the adoption of participatory methods, there is a need to *optimise* the use of participatory approaches in agricultural research (our emphases). To this end, they developed a new participation framework that paid particular attention to the characteristics of researchers and local stakeholders and to their various forms of interaction.

Unlike Neef and Neubert (2011), who studied their own research programmes in South-East Asia and Africa, we reviewed 200 contrasting multi-actor co-innovation partnerships from across Europe, a region in which the EU’s agenda of ‘speeding up’ innovation through financial support for multi-actor projects dominates the agricultural innovation policy discourse (EIP AGRI SP, 2017; Fieldsend et al., 2021). While many of these partnerships were indeed funded by the EU, our analysis also included a substantial number of ‘under the radar’ partnerships (including many of those identified through the EURIC), several of which were not ‘projects’ and/or did not call upon external funding. The resulting dataset has allowed us to shed new light on the complexity of co-innovation processes in agriculture, forestry and related sectors.

⁴ Van Lancker et al. (2016) defines a regional innovation system (p.41) as “an interrelationship of innovation actors [i.e. the AKIS] and institutions [i.e. the enabling environment] in a particular region that enables the generation, diffusion, and appropriation of innovation”.

As a framework for analysing this complexity, we have constructed a multidimensional conceptual typology of multi-actor co-innovation activities. The overarching concept measured by this typology is ‘effectiveness of co-innovation by a multi-actor partnership’. This concept has two dimensions which incorporate the main traits that shape a co-innovation activity. These traits are, in line with the OIS concept of Van Lancker et al. (2016), the attitude of the actors towards interaction, the form of the (co-)innovation process adopted by the partnership, the ways in which the partnership engages with the wider AKIS, and its attitude towards dealing with the institutions of the enabling environment. The result is a matrix of eight ideal types of co-innovation activity, each named according to its corresponding concept (Fig. 1).

The typology illustrates that the co-innovation process can take contrasting forms, as determined by numerous factors including actor capacities, aspirations and networks, the co-innovation topic and its influence on the size of the partnership and structure of the workplan, the type of co-innovation activity outputs and the consequent need to engage with the larger periphery of stakeholders, and the nature of the enabling environment. In line with Neef and Neubert (2011), the typology strongly challenges the assumption that more interaction is necessarily ‘better’. It is possible for ‘indifference’ towards interaction,⁵ whether among the actors, during the co-innovation process, with external stakeholders and/or with the enabling environment, to be a legitimate strategy for ‘speeding up’ innovation.

The fact that this is a conceptual and not an explanatory typology needs to be clearly restated here. The methodology demands that there should be internal consistency among the first-order constructs within an ideal type (Doty and Glick, 1994). This constraint leads to some associations which at first sight might be unexpected. For example, most European universities would claim to promote gender inclusion in their multi-actor co-innovation activities. At the same time, it is almost certainly true that in most instances the primary driver for their participation in such activities is the availability of external (co-)funding. Yet, these two approaches are features of different types in the typology. The reason for this is that promotion of gender inclusion is interpreted as ‘fostering interaction’ (with a diversity of individuals) while inclusion solely on merit could be viewed as being ‘indifferent towards interaction’. In the case of motivation for interaction, the desire to find a solution to a problem may reflect a desire to foster interaction, whereas participation in partnerships in response to the primary need to secure external funding may indicate indifference towards interaction.

Our typology represents a theory to be tested and potentially falsified. Doty and Glick (1994) listed three important implications for typological theories that concern their testing. Firstly, the ideal types represent organisational forms that *might* exist rather than real partnerships. In other words, it is in the very nature of a typology that the descriptions are presented as ‘extremes’ and empirical examples of ideal-type organisations are likely to be rare or non-existent. Secondly, the ideal types are complex phenomena that must be described in terms of multiple dimensions. Thirdly, each ideal-type organisation represents a unique combination of the dimensions used to describe the set of ideal types. Each of our 200 reviewed partnerships *may be more or less similar* to an ideal type, cannot be assigned to specific types.

This points up the first of two ‘limitations’ of our research, namely that our typology cannot be used to classify individual co-innovation activities. In the literature, the terms ‘classification scheme’, ‘taxonomy’ and ‘typology’ have frequently been used interchangeably (Doty and Glick, 1994). Fotheringham et al. (2016), for example, attempted to ‘classify’ EU Rural Development Programmes according to a ‘typology’. But the first two terms categorise phenomena into mutually exclusive and exhaustive sets with a series of discrete decision rules; unlike typologies, they do not identify a unique and distinct set of ideal types.

6.2. Policy implications and future work

The insights afforded by the typology are of value to four groups of actors which are analogous to those identified by Kujala et al. (2021) for the rural business support policy regime under the EU’s Common Agricultural Policy. Three of these groups have policy and/or programming functions. ‘European Union (EU) level policy makers’ shape not just the EIP-AGRI but also other programmes that foster co-innovation such as Interreg and LIFE. ‘Policy makers at national (and regional) level’ have responsibility for their own (agricultural) innovation programmes including those funded by EU Rural Development Programmes. ‘Policy implementers at national, regional and local levels’ determine the effectiveness of implementation of the programmes framed by policy. The analytical framework provided by our study will help all three groups (and their non-EU counterparts) to develop more targeted interventions, according to actor needs and local circumstances, for ‘speeding up’ innovation.

Firstly, there is potential to improve the implementation of the ‘multi-actor approach’. The EU requires projects to “focus on real problems or opportunities that farmers, foresters or others who need a solution (‘end-users’) are facing” and “partners with complementary types of knowledge – scientific, practical and other – must join forces in the project activities from beginning to end” (EIP AGRI SP, 2017, p.2). These requirements are frequently interpreted as meaning that all the necessary knowledge should be represented in the core consortium, despite many actor groups (especially practitioners) being discouraged by the administrative demands of consortium membership. We have shown, firstly, that many co-innovation partnerships are interlinked and are already familiar with user needs through previous activities and, secondly, that the co-innovation activity involves not just the core partnership but also the larger periphery of engaged stakeholders. More attention could be given to implementing alternative approaches to fostering effective knowledge sharing between the consortium and the periphery.

Secondly, the ‘project’ is the ‘methodology of choice’ for the EU (although even these vary from large, international projects to smaller, local OGs) and many other funding agencies. But many actors choose to co-innovate through programmes, clusters/cooperatives, value chain networks or single entrepreneur initiatives. More administrative and financial support for these alternative actor configurations may contribute to the policy goal of ‘speeding up’ innovation.

The fourth group, innovation actors,⁶ i.e. the AKIS actors who participate in co-innovation activities, such as farmers, researchers, advisors and value chain actors, can obtain clearer insights into the contrasting motivations of other groups of actors with whom they should collaborate. They can also adopt alternative and potentially more effective ways to foster actor inclusion and greater knowledge sharing between the consortium and the periphery.

Beyond the EU, the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) runs projects that may span different continents (de Janvry and Kassam, 2004). But other actor configurations for co-innovation are numerous and diverse, including, for example, Arena SKOG, a value-chain driven wood- and forestry-based innovation cluster located in the Trøndelag region of Norway,⁷ farmer field schools in Asia and Africa (Davis et al., 2009) and the various participatory plant breeding programmes worldwide (Vernooij et al., 2009). Klerix et al. (2017) highlighted the importance of the institutional context in which the participatory research is carried out, noting that it co-determines effectiveness, and this observation illustrates a second limitation of our research. The 200 co-innovation partnerships, although diverse in nature and identified from several sources, represent only a fraction of the whole and, despite the good results from the EURIC, many activities

⁵ In contrast to ‘indifference’ towards co-innovation, as stated earlier.

⁶ Kujala et al. (2021) listed ‘rural entrepreneurs’ in lieu of ‘innovation actors’.

⁷ <https://www.ntnu.edu/wood/arena-skog>

that are not included in databases will have escaped our notice. Additional testing of the typology, especially its applicability to non-European examples of co-innovation partnerships, will contribute to its further refinement.

Klerkx et al. (2017) reported that different institutional levels (personal, organisational and national agricultural innovation system) and dimensions cannot be seen in isolation but are interlinked and reinforce one another in how they constrain participatory research. They showed that caution is needed when replicating or exporting participatory research approaches from one context to another. Similarly, Cronin et al. (2022) argued that the analytical integration of the micro- and macro-level innovation systems perspectives is necessary to understand fully the mechanisms underlying the functioning of the co-innovation process. They explored this idea further by developing a Multi-Level Innovation Framework (MINOS) which they applied to 50 multi-actor H2020 projects. Multi-level system failures which occurred during the consortium development, implementation and stakeholder involvement and dissemination phases of these projects helped to identify the root causes of both their successes and failures.

The work of Cronin et al. (2022) initiated the development of a conceptual vocabulary for system failures and blocking mechanisms which cross different innovation system boundaries. However, their analysis was (of necessity) confined to one specific type of 'project'. The results from our paper provide pointers for further research on this topic which would support the drafting of more targeted recommendations for interventions to support the functioning of co-innovation processes in agriculture, forestry and related sectors.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

The data that have been used are confidential.

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